

PHAETHON Teaming Project

Version 0

Description

The data management plan (DMP) of the PHAETHON project is a comprehensive document outlining how research data will be collected, organized, stored, shared, and preserved throughout the project's lifecycle. It provides a systematic approach to managing data, ensuring its integrity, security, and accessibility while adhering to ethical and legal standards. The DMP addresses key aspects such as data collection methods, metadata standards, storage and backup procedures, data sharing and access policies, long-term preservation strategies, roles and responsibilities of project team members, and compliance with relevant regulations and guidelines. By establishing clear guidelines and protocols for data management, the DMP helps researchers maximize the value and impact of their data, promote transparency and reproducibility, and facilitate collaboration and knowledge exchange within the research community.

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PHAETHON Research and
Innovation Centre of
Excellence for Intelligent,
Efficient and Sustainable
Energy Solutions

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Organizations

University of Groningen, University of Cyprus, Cyprus Seeds,
Technical University Denmark

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: PHAETHON Teaming Project

Description:

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[University of Groningen](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Horizon Europe - European Commission](#)

Grants: [PHAETHON Research and Innovation Centre of Excellence for Intelligent, Efficient and Sustainable Energy Solutions](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

PHAETHON Teaming Project data

Data generated/collected by the PHAETHON Teaming project.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1.1 Brief description of the described research output

1.1.1 What kind of research output are you describing?

Research Data

1.1.2 Is it physical or digital?

Digital

1.1.3 Are you generating or re-using it?

New

The data generated within the project is new data.

1.1.4 What is the type of the described dataset?

Experimental

The data is generated from the on-site data acquisition devices installed at the outdoor testing facilities of the Smart Energy Infrastructure | PHAETHON CoE.

1.1.5 What is its format?

Extensible Markup Language (.xml)

Comma-separated tables (.csv)

1.1.6 What is its expected size?

1 MB

1.1.7 Why are you collecting/generating or re-using it?

- To obtain information
- To make informed decisions
- To develop a product

The data provides information on the operation of a test-bed photovoltaic (PV) system.

The information provided by the data is useful to fulfill the following project objectives:

To gain insights on the operation and performance of PV systems.

To develop predictive performance models.

1.1.8 What is its origin / provenance?

The origin is a test-bed experimental PV system (1 kWp capacity) installed at the Smart Energy Infrastructure | PHAETHON CoE.

1.1.9 To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

- Researchers
- Research communities
- Education
- Industry

The data is useful for research, educational; and industrial purposes since it can be used to:

- Enhance predictive performance models.
- Provide useful training on the performance of renewable systems and applied.

2.1 Publications

2.1.1 Does the described output support any scientific publication?

No

2.1.2 Is there a data availability statement provided along with the publication?

No

2.3 Software

2.3.1 Does the described output use or support any software?

No

3.1.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

3.1.1.1 What type(s) of persistent identifier(s) are used for the described dataset / output?

- Data identifiers
- Organizations identifiers
- Projects identifiers

DOI

GRID

Cordis

3.1.1.2 Will you provide metadata for the described dataset / output?

Yes

CERIF (Common European Research Information Format)

3.1.1.3 What type(s) of metadata?

Descriptive

3.1.1.4 Do the metadata use standardised vocabularies?

No

3.1.1.6 Are the metadata searchable?

Yes

3.1.1.7 How are searchable metadata provided?

- Registry/Catalogue
- Metadata repository
- Content Management System

3.1.1.8 Are keywords provided in the metadata?

Yes

energy, performance, prediction

3.1.1.9 Are metadata harvestable?

Yes

The metadata are exchanged in support by the OAI-PMH protocol.

3.2.1 Repository

3.2.1.1 In which repository will the dataset / output be deposited?

Zenodo | PHAETHON CoE

<https://zenodo.org/communities/phaethon/>

3.2.1.2 Is the selected repository a trusted source?

Yes

- Has certification
- Follows repository standards
- Details terms of use
- Has an open access content policy
- Supports retention

3.2.1.5 Does the repository(ies) assign datasets / outputs with persistent identifiers?

Yes

3.2.1.7 Does the repository support versioning?

Yes

3.2.2 Data

3.2.2.1 What is the described dataset / output title?

Test-bed PV system performance data

3.2.2.2 How is the dataset / output shared?

Open

3.2.2.5 Are there any methods or tools required to access the dataset / output?

No

3.2.2.8 Is the described dataset / output supported by a data access committee?

Yes

3.2.3 Metadata

3.2.3.1 Will you provide metadata even if the described dataset / output can not be openly shared?

Yes

3.2.3.2 Under which license will metadata be provided?

Creative Commons Zero (CC0)

3.2.3.3 Do metadata provide information about how to access the described dataset / output?

Yes

3.2.3.4 Will metadata remain available after the dataset / output is no longer available?

No

3.3 Making data and other outputs interoperable

3.3.1 Does your (meta)data use a controlled vocabulary?

Yes

3.3.3 Have you applied a standard schema for your (meta)data?

Yes

CERIF (Common European Research Information Format)

3.4 Increasing data and other outputs reuse

3.4.1 What internationally recognised licence will you use for your dataset / output?

- Attribution Assurance Licenses
- GNU Lesser General Public License 3.0

3.4.3 Will you provide the described dataset / output in the public domain?

Yes

3.4.4 Do you intend to ensure (re)use by third parties after your project finishes?

Yes

3.4.5 Is provenance well documented?

Yes

3.4.6 What documented procedures for quality assurance do you have in place?

- Use of tools for automatic checks
- Data conform to format specification
- Consistency verified with data models and standards

4.1 Allocation of resources

4.1.1 What will be the cost of making the described output FAIR?

500

Euro

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security

Direct cost

4.1.2 How will this cost be covered?

Other

4.1.3 Identify the people who will be responsible and their role(s) in the management of the described output

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5.1 Data Security

5.1.1 What security measures are followed?

Encryption

5.1.2 What conditions do the security measures meet?

- Data storage
- Data transmission

6.1 Ethical aspects

6.1.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on sharing the described dataset / output?

no

6.1.2 Does the described dataset / output contain sensitive information?

No

7.1 Other

7.1.1 Do you make use of other procedures for data management?

No

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